

ROCK-CUT TEMPLE BY PAUL KLEE AND LINA BO BARDI: PARALLEL WORLDS OF IMAGINATION

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SUMMARY

In 1951, Pietro Maria Bardi, the director of the Museu de Arte de São Paulo (MASP), planned the first solo exhibition of Paul Klee in Brazil. For this purpose, the gallerist Suzanne Feigel brought 32 works to Brazil. However, the exhibition was delayed due to problems with the customs clearance. Additionally, concerns were raised that Klee's small-scale paintings would be lost in the extensive, open exhibition space of MASP. Attempts to borrow additional works failed due to high costs and conservation reasons. Nonetheless, Klee's drawing *Rock-Cut Temple*, 1925, 251 came into the

possession of the architect Lina Bo Bardi. It turns out that there is a remarkable connection between this work and Bardi's own residence, the *Casa de Vidro* (Glass House) in São Paulo. While Klee's drawing transport viewers into an imaginary world filled with mysterious architectures, Bardi's Glass House creates a unique link between interior and exterior spaces. It seamlessly integrates with the surrounding nature and invites entirely new perceptual experiences. In 1953, Klee was finally given his first exhibition in Brazil at the II São Paulo Biennial.

SUZANNE FEIGEL'S BRAZIL ART EXPEDITION

In an endeavour to offer a comprehensive insight into Paul Klee's body of work to audiences across Brazil, the Basel-based art dealer Suzanne Feigel (FIG. 1) embarked on a significant journey. On 3 May, 1951, Feigel set sail from Genoa on the Atlantic steamer *Conte Grande* (FIG. 2), her destination being Rio de Janeiro.¹

She was travelling with a crate containing 32 works, including 24 by Paul Klee, as well as pieces by Picasso, Miró, André Derain, Giorgio de Chirico, Yves Tanguy, and Marc Chagall.² These works were not only intended for a sales exhibition at MASP,³ the Museu de Arte de São Paulo, but also served as a representation

of how Brazil was engaging with the Bauhaus movement at the time.⁴

It was to be the first exhibition of Klee's original works in Brazil, curated by the museum's director, Pietro Maria Bardi.⁵ The pieces originated from Feigel's Galerie d'Art Moderne in Basel and other galleries in France, Italy, and Germany.⁶ The goal of the exhibition was to curate an exhibition providing a representative overview of Klee's oeuvre and opening access to Klee's work for audiences not only from São Paulo but also from the entire country.⁷

ARRIVAL IN BRAZIL AND CUSTOMS CHALLENGES

Two weeks later,⁸ Feigel arrived at the port of Rio de Janeiro, where she was re-

Fig. 1
The gallerist Marie-Suzanne Feigel, Basel,
1953, photographer: Maria Netter
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Fig. 2
Postcard depicting Port of Genoa, M/N Conte
Grande departing, 1951, photographer
unknown, private collection, Künsnacht

ceived by her friend Lydia Alimonda Haller, a pianist with whom she had previously spent time in Basel. She was able to stay with Haller during her time in Rio.⁹ Due to the missing import permits, the crates containing the artworks were held at customs in Rio for six weeks.¹⁰ Only after declaring the paintings as a “gift to the museum” and thanks to the intervention of the Brazilian Minister of Finance, Horácio Lafer, their importation was finally facilitated.¹¹

LINGUISTIC AND CONCEPTUAL CHALLENGES AT MASP

After the six-week mandatory stay in Rio, the now-released works arrived in São

Paulo, and conversations with the museum began, as Feigel recalls in her memories. These discussions were extremely difficult, as they were conducted in five different languages: Bardi communicated exclusively in Italian and Portuguese; one secretary understood only German and Italian; another only French and Portuguese; and a third spoke English and Portuguese.¹² Bardi emphasized that the sizes of the Klee artworks were too small for an exhibition, especially in a room of 450 square meters. “In there, the 24 small sheets would be completely lost,” he said.¹³ Pietro Maria Bardi and his museum team were eager to acquire additional works of art. To this end, they engaged in negotiations with the Museum of Modern Art in New York to secure the loan of a set of lithographs and reached out to Curt Valentin in New York in order to obtain a “group of lithographs”¹⁴ from his extensive collection of Klee works. Valentin agreed to loan his works on the condition that they would be framed and displayed behind glass. However, these conditions were too costly for the Museu de Arte de São Paulo and apparently contradicted the museum’s exhibition philosophy.

Fig. 3
Lina Bo and Pietro Maria Bardi upon arrival
at Congonhas Airport, São Paulo, 1947,
photographer unknown
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Fig. 4a
Picture Gallery, MASP, Rua 7 de Abril, São
Paulo, 1947, photographer unknown, MASP
Research Center Collection
© MASP

Fig. 4b
View of the MASP collection in the museum's
original premises at Rua 7 de Abril;
exhibition design by Lina Bo Bardi, 1950,
photographer: Luiz Hossaka, MASP
Research Center Collection
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THE VISION OF PIETRO MARIA BARDI AND LINA BO BARDI: DEMOCRATIZATION AND INNOVATION AT MASP

In 1947, the Italian-born Pietro Maria Bardi, along with Assis Chateaubriand, founded the Museu de São Paulo (MASP) that he directed until 1996. The museum's new building, inaugurated in 1968, was designed by the architect Lina Bo Bardi (FIG. 3), the wife of Pietro Maria Bardi.¹⁵

The approach of the Bardis to the democratization of museums and the accessibility of art have garnered attention. Together with her husband, Lina Bo Bardi designed an open exhibition space where paintings were displayed on glass easels, enabling a panoramic view and creating the impression of floating artworks. To address the hierarchical distinctions in historical reception – the dichotomy between 'high' and 'low' art – the Bardis devised an innovative approach. This was influenced by the museum designs of Italian architects like Franco Albini, the architectural group BBPR founded in 1932, and Carlo Scarpa. The Bardis had previously experimented with similar exhibition concepts in a preceding building of MASP (FIGS. 4a, 4b).¹⁶

In contrast to the European context where works are integrated into the established art historical narrative based on their value, it was the artwork itself in MASP that reshaped the historical narrative. According to the approach of the Bardis, the artworks should be considered equal and arranged "democratically" side by side, allowing each work to make its own contribution. This principle underlies the decision to replace the traditional sequence of rooms with a continuous space. The Bardis might have been inspired by Frank Lloyd Wright's revolutionary exhibition system for the Guggenheim Museum in New York. Frank Lloyd Wright conceived the Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum as a spiral tower to provide an engaging experience of modern art. Rather than arranging the paintings in a conventional manner, the museum's design allows viewers to experience the artworks while moving along the ascending spiral path, enabling a top-to-bottom visual journey.¹⁷

Lina Bo Bardi's design approach for MASP was intended to broaden the accessibility of artworks to a diverse audience. The works at MASP are displayed on transparent glass easels, creating the il-

Fig. 4c
Picture Gallery of MASP after the new building's inauguration in 1968, photographer: Luiz Hossaka, MASP Research Center Collection © MASP

In the catalogue of the current show, James Thrall Soby says: "Indeed, perhaps only Picasso among modern painters has rivaled Klee in the ability to translate into new visual terms what is primarily a psychological or even a moral point . . . And allowing for its deliberate humility, Klee's art seems as rich in plastic discovery as Picasso's."

Paul Klee, an honored prophet

Fig. 5
Excerpt from the article [Anonym], "Traveling Klee," in: *Newsweek*, 2 January, 1950, p. 54
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

clusion that the paintings are floating in the space. This design allows viewers to look at the paintings from all sides and move freely in the space, rather than being forced to view them in a specific order or direction.

Moreover, it is a democratic way of representing art, as no hierarchy exists between the paintings – they all share the same space and are displayed in the same way (FIG. 4c). Lina Bo Bardi had placed the labels containing information about the artworks on the backside of the transparent easels. This unique design allowed viewers to focus entirely on the artwork itself before engaging with the accompanying information. The juxtaposition of works from different epochs and geographic regions played an important educational role.¹⁸ This radical style of presentation was a break from the traditional ways of exhibiting art. The works do not demand admiration but instead offer viewers the opportunity for an unprejudiced observation.

THE EXHIBITION THAT NEVER TOOK PLACE: THE FAILURE OF THE FIRST EXHIBITION IN BRAZIL

Originally, Pietro Maria Bardi intended to show works by Paul Klee from the 1949/50 U.S. travelling exhibition in São Paulo. The targeted promotion of the global reception of Klee's work in the post-war period had begun with a series of solo exhibitions of Paul Klee in Germany, organized by the Klee Society. This organization played a significant role in providing Klee's works to various art dealers, thereby initiating numerous sales exhibitions. In parallel, the Klee Society launched a travelling exhibition that was shown not only in six European cities but also in fifteen American cities.¹⁹

The U.S. tour of this notable travelling exhibition showcased paintings, drawings, and prints mainly from the Klee Foundation in Bern. These were supplemented by works from American collections, and the show was displayed in many prestigious museums, including the San Francisco Museum of Art and the Museum of Modern Art in New York.²⁰ Although the exhibition received considerable press attention (FIG. 5),²¹ it is rarely mentioned in specialized Klee literature.²² Before this U.S. tour, a large Klee exhibition was held at the Kunsthhaus Zürich,²³ where Max Bill was responsible for the display of Klee's works.²⁴ Despite Bill's intent, his opening speech garnered mixed reviews, with some Swiss press articles suggesting that it was dismissive of Klee's work.²⁵ During this time, Bardi, on the advice of Porter McCray, the director of the Museum of Modern Art, contacted Rolf Bürgi, who had been instrumental in founding the Paul Klee Foundation and had a long-standing relationship with the Klee family. Bardi approached him to discuss the possibility of including the Klee exhibition in Brazil in the overseas tour (FIG. 6).²⁶ Despite Bardi's interest in the exhibition, the Klee Society decided in

Fig. 6
Letter from the Museu de Arte (Pietro Maria Bardi) to Rolf Bürgi, 5 September, 1949, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bürgi Family Donation
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

March 1950 not to extend their loans to American museums any longer. This was intended to protect the artworks from further transport risks and to make them accessible to the public in the Museum of Fine Arts Bern soon.²⁷

Amidst these developments, Bardi heard about a planned Paul Klee exhibition at the Instituto de Arte Moderno (IAM) in Buenos Aires. In light of this, Szabolcs de Vajay,²⁸ the Director of the Instituto de Arte Moderno in Buenos Aires from 1948–1954, proposed a collaboration between MASP and IAM. This gained particular significance as the Paul Klee Foundation had committed to send 50 paintings and drawings by air freight in July 1951.²⁹ Nevertheless, Bardi declined the offered partnership, as he was already negotiating with Suzanne Feigel of the Galerie

d'Art Moderne in Basel and perhaps already knew of the Paul Klee Foundation's decision not to provide Klee's works on loan anymore.³⁰

The circumstances surrounding the planned Paul Klee exhibition in São Paulo were complex. Despite well-advanced preparations, including plans to translate Klee's work titles into Portuguese as well as an article by Italo Faldi³¹ promoting the exhibition in the third issue of the magazine *Habitat* (1951), Bardi ultimately had to declare the project a failure in late July 1951.³² These preparations also included an intended Portuguese translation of Paul Klee's *On Modern Art*³³ set to be published in collaboration with Benteli-Verlag in Bern.³⁴ Despite all these efforts, the exhibition was cancelled due to a lack of available artworks and financial difficulties. Feigel, who was set to visit the exhibition in São Paulo, was disappointed by the news.

A letter from the secretariat of P. M. Bardi to Suzanne-Marie Feigel elaborates that various factors contributed to this decision, including a cancellation by the Museum of Modern Art in New York.³⁵

The reasons why prominent works from the Paul Klee Foundation could not be loaned for the São Paulo exhibition may also lie in the exclusive collaboration of the Paul Klee Society with the Rosengart Gallery, to the detriment of the Feigel Gallery. However, this remains subject to further investigation.

As the planned Klee show at MASP did not take place, the first exhibition featuring original works by Klee in Brazil finally took place in 1953, organized by a new team as part of the II Biennale of São Paulo and showcasing an entirely different set of works.³⁶

THE UNCONVENTIONAL REPATRIATION OF THE ARTWORKS TO SWITZERLAND

During the repatriation of the artworks in late summer 1951, several challenges

Liste des Oeuvres contenues dans la caisse G.A.M. No. 1 destinées à l'Exposition "Au Museu de Arte São Paulo."

<u>Oeuvres de Paul Klee.</u>		<u>Année</u>	<u>Dimensions</u>	<u>Valeur</u>
<u>Technique</u>	<u>Titre</u>	<u>No.</u>	<u>cm.</u>	<u>Frs. R.</u>
1. Aquarell	Haus am Kanal	1912/105	19,5-13,5	1.500.-
2. Aquarell	Sans titre	1915/247	26 - 9	1.200.-
3. Aquarell	Monsieur Perlenschwein	1923/ W 3	52 -35	3.500.-
4. Dessin à ping.	Wassersaun	1940/H 10	42 -30	2.000.-
5. Aquarell/Temp.	Nördlicher Ort	1923/73	35 -25	3.500.-
6. Aquarell	Sans titre	env.1917	32 -24	2.500.-
* 7. Aquarell	Die Aeelsharfe	1922/89	21,5-16,2	3.000.-
* 8. Aquarell	Tänzerpaar	1923/126	20,5-15,5	3.000.-
* 9. Dessin	Mittelalterliche Stadt, aq.	1924/168	35 -21	1.500.-
10. Aquarell	Perellenbach	env.1917	24 -12	2.000.-
11. Tafelbild	Südalpiner Ort	1923/26	32 -18	2.500.-
12. Huile s.papier	Musik unter Tag	1940/15	52 -35	5.000.-
13. Aquarell	Pflanzen auf der Lauer	1925/m5	28 -22	2.000.-
14. Aquarell	Compositien	1914/18	17 -16	2.000.-
15. Dessin	Felsentempel	1925/Z.1.	26 -16	800.-
16. Dessin	Idee wie ein Haus "Tneun"	1925	15 -12,5	800.-
17. Eau forte	Höhe	1928/1/10	50 -37	350.-
18. Litho celerée	Der Park (45 sur 200)	1914/145	27 -18,5	250.-
* 19. Litho celerée	Der Verliebte (Probedr.)	1923/91	30 -23,5	500.-
* 20. Litho celerée	Der Seiltänzer	1923/138	52 -36	350.-
* 21. Litho originale	Die Riesenblattlaus		32,5-24	150.-
* 22. Eau forte	Kleinwelt	1914/120	42 -32	150.-
* 23. Litho	Tragödie auf Stelzen	1912/119	15 -15	150.-
24. Litho celerée	Im Geiste Hoffmanns	1921/123	35,5-25,5	350.-
<u>Oeuvres de Pablo Picasso.</u>				
25. Huile-Geuache	Tête	12.I.42	40 -30	5.000.-
26. Geuache	Dame en fauteuil	1917	31 -20	3.500.-
<u>Oeuvres des</u>				
	<u>Technique</u>	<u>Titre</u>		
27. Juan Mirò	Dessin à l'encre de chine		28 -20,5	1.000.-
28. Juan Mirò	Dessin au crayon		63 -46	700.-
29. André Derain	huile Marine		31 -17	2.500.-
30. De Chirice	huile Mécanique		60 -50	7.000.-
31. Yves Tanguy	huile 1939		55 -45	3.000.-
32. Marc Chagall	huile Le paysan 1914		73 -55	8.000.-
Valeur totale				Frs.8.69.750.-

Fig. 7

Paul Feigel (Galerie d'Art Moderne in Basel), list of works for the exhibition at the Museu de Arte São Paulo, 26.04.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo

Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

arose that required immediate attention. Feigel faced the challenge of how to return pieces to Switzerland that were not owned by the gallery but were on consignment (FIG. 7).³⁷ And after all, the works had been declared as a "gift to the museum [MASP]" upon entry into Brazil. The surprising solution for this problem of repatriation was to carefully pack each artwork and send two to three pieces in yellow envelopes by mail to Basel, by-passing Brazilian customs.³⁸ Naturally, the co-owner of Feigel's gallery was concerned about this unconventional approach, but fortunately, all the envelopes arrived in Switzerland undamaged.³⁹

One large oil painting, *Musik unter Tag*, 1940, 235, however, could not fit in the envelopes. But a friend of the Feigels, the previously mentioned pianist Lydia Alimonda Haller who had the privilege to travel with a larger suitcase due to her VIP status, offered to bring the "panel painting" to Basel on her next voyage aboard the *Compte Grande*.⁴⁰

According to Feigel's recollection, even though the initial goal of staging a "major Klee exhibition" in São Paulo was not met, the venture was far from a financial failure. The subsequent sale of the painting *Musik unter Tag* not only covered the travel expenses but also exceeded them. This

Fig. 9
Pietro Maria Bardi, "Aonde vai a Pintura?"
["Where is Painting Going?"], in: *Habitat: revista das artes no Brasil*, vol. 15, March/
April 1954, p. 45
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern,
Archive

Fig. 8
Paul Klee, *Felsen Tempel* [Rock-Cut Temple],
1925, 251, pen and black ink on buff laid
paper, laid down on artist's mount
comprised of cream wove card ruled in pen
and black ink, 16.4 x 26.9 cm, The Art
Institute of Chicago, gift of Dorothy Braude
Edinburg to the Harry B. and Bessie K.
Braude Memorial Collection
© akg-images

specific artwork had previously garnered attention from the Stuttgart Museum, leading to a sale that fetched a sum far greater than the original purchase price. Despite all the challenges of the trip, Feigel found the experience in Brazil overwhelmingly enriching, being captivated by the country's red soil, lush jungles, expansive beaches, and towering palm trees.⁴¹

**PARALLEL WORLDS OF IMAGINATION:
PAUL KLEE'S ROCK-CUT TEMPLE AND
LINA BO BARDI'S CASA DE VIDRO**

It remains an open research question whether all 32 artworks that Feigel brought to Brazil actually left the country.⁴² However, it is certain that the drawing *Felsen Tempel* (Rock-Cut Temple), 1925, 251 (FIG. 8), came into the possession of architect Lina Bo Bardi in the early 1950s, as evidenced by a provenance note in an article by Piero Maria Bardi in the

journal *Habitat* in 1954 (FIG. 9).⁴³ Lina Bo Bardi served as the editor and co-publisher of the magazine.⁴⁴ The drawing was either a gift from her husband or was acquired by her personally.

PROVENANCE AND INTERSECTION: THE JOURNEY OF KLEE'S FELSEN TEMPLE TO LINA BO BARDI

It's no coincidence that Lina Bo Bardi's Klee work from the Feigel collection represents specifically the Bauhaus Dessau period. Toward the end of 1925, Klee began working on landscape-architectural drawings with parallel linear layers, an expressive form in which he achieved the highest level of mastery the following year.⁴⁵

In these works, Klee takes the viewer to imaginary places filled with mysterious buildings and monuments, sanctuaries, temples, tombs, and palaces. Also the architect Philip C. Johnson owned a Klee work of this genre, *Heilige Inseln* (*Sacred*

Islands), 1926, 6 (FIG. 10).⁴⁶ This piece belongs to a group of works that Klee created between 1925 and 1927, known as "Parallelfigurationen" (Parallel Figurations) – a term coined by Christian Geelhaar.⁴⁷ This series consists of compositions that employ the graphic language of parallel lines to create shapes and spaces, and it is theoretically grounded in Klee's Bauhaus teachings.⁴⁸ Klee built his Bauhaus teaching on the basis of nature studies, with the belief that this approach would lead students to "freely create abstract forms."⁴⁹ Like a leaf shaped by the energy coursing through its veins, the forms and structures in the drawing *Felsen Tempel* (*Rock-Cut Temple*) emerge from the connection and integration of parallel lines that seem to be assembled without explicit intent.⁵⁰

Rock-Cut Temple serves as a prime example of the methodical use of lines, reflecting Paul Klee's artistic thought during his time at the Weimar Bauhaus. In this work, the use of parallel lines creates a complex scene resembling a prehistoric architecture as if carved into rock.⁵¹ There are mysterious portals, stairs, and paths, as well as routes seemingly etched into the rock. These lead to hidden monuments, such as ancient ruins carved into the rock or mysterious shrines dedicated to forgotten deities. The pattern of parallel lines generates a rhythm that guides the viewer's eye through the artwork and stimulates the imagination. Klee believed that the roots of modern art partially lay in prehistory. For him, prehistory was a time when art emerged directly from the perception of the world and not from rational concepts. Klee aspired to return modern art to this more primal form of artistic expression. Klee aspired to return modern art to this more primal form of artistic expression. For Klee, it was not the result or the form that mattered, but rather the creative process and the infinite possibilities arising through the use of line.

Fig. 10
Paul Klee, *Heilige Inseln* [*Sacred Islands*], 1926, 6, ink and watercolour on paper on board, 63.2 x 47 cm, Museum of Modern Art, New York, gift of Philip Johnson
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

EXPLORING AESTHETIC LANGUAGES: PARALLEL LINES AND SPATIAL PERCEPTION IN KLEE'S AND BO BARDI'S WORKS

In his lectures at the Bauhaus, Klee outlined various design techniques based on the principle of two intersecting triangles (FIG. 11), reminiscent of a weaving pattern.⁵³ The weaving process starts with a collection of threads that are interwoven according to a specific pattern. This process mirrors Klee's method in the creation of his abstract-graphic art. He began with a palette of colours and shapes which he then linked in a particular pattern. According to Osamu Okuda, these approaches can be traced back to the origins of art, as highlighted by Gottfried Semper, as well as to weaving as one of the oldest and most important textile techniques.⁵⁴ Klee's method of "Parallel Figurations," in which overlapping and interpenetrating forms merge into a complex whole, serves as an example of this connection.

In his theory of cladding, Gottfried Semper argues that the aesthetic representation of materials and constructions is essential for conveying cultural identity. For Semper, textile art was the primal art form, from which all other art forms – including architecture – have developed their types and symbols (FIG. 12).⁵⁵

Irrespective of the connection between textile art and architecture (as posited by Semper), textile weaving techniques are a central theme in the reception of Klee's abstract-graphic works, which are often likened to carpets. Although Klee's "decorative" style of painting and drawing was often perceived merely as "[carpet] design,"⁵⁶ it is worth noting that he consistently sought to establish a relationship between painting and textile art, particularly in the context of his teaching role in the Weaving Department of the Weimar Bauhaus.⁵⁷ Nevertheless, Jenny Anger emphasizes that these compositions

Fig. 11
Paul Klee, "Bildnerische Gestaltungslehre [Theory of Pictorial Configuration]: II. 13 Irreguläres Formgebilde [Irregular Form]," pencil and coloured pencil on paper, 33 x 21 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, inv. no. BG II.13/30
Note: Bottom of the sheet slightly cropped © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 12
Egyptian latticework, illustration in: Gottfried Semper, *Der Stil in den technischen und tektonischen Künsten oder praktische Ästhetik: Ein Handbuch für Techniker Künstler und Kunst*, vol. 1, p. 177
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

It would not be entirely accurate to speak of a "theory" by Klee, as he did not actually develop a comprehensive theory of art.⁵² His views and beliefs were more focused on his artistic practice and the creative process. He placed great emphasis on the creative process and the infinite possibilities that arose from the application of lines, rather than on the end result or form. This was reflected in his artistic practice in which he often used nature as an instructive model. The concept of distinguishing between form and formation through the use of line is a significant element in this approach. *The Rock-Cut Temple* serves as a compelling example of this methodology.

Fig. 13
Lina Bo Bardi's *Casa de Vidro*, 1951, São Paulo, photographer: Peter Scheier, in: *Domus*, no. 279, February 1953, p. 19
© Peter Scheier/Instituto Lina Bo e PM Bardi

should by no means be confused with an actual carpet.⁵⁸

On this foundation, Klee designed his sacred, mythological landscapes of "Parallel Figurations" in which the awareness of the classical-antique heritage plays a crucial role. He deliberately embraced this heritage as part of European culture and linked it with Christian layers of meaning. This is reflected in Klee's *Felsen Tempel* in which he portrays the landscape as a significant expression of Christian art. According to Christian Geelhaar, this approach is deeply rooted in the tradition of German Early Romanticism, adding additional depth and complexity to Klee's work.⁵⁹

The research by Geelhaar and Okuda on Klee and the method of "parallel figurations" in connection with textiles and architecture provides also a valuable perspective for understanding Klee's piece *Felsen Tempel*.

In 1951, when the Bardis moved into their new residence *Casa de Vidro* in the district of Jardim do Morumbi in São Paulo (FIG. 13), they came into possession of Klee's drawing. There is a remark-

able connection between the *Casa de Vidro*, designed by Lina Bo Bardi,⁶⁰ and Paul Klee's drawing *Felsen Tempel*. Both artworks explore the interactive process between interior and exterior spaces. The distinction between the interior and the exterior is increasingly blurred, lending the space a sense of "fluidity," as it is no longer distinctly separated by material boundaries.

Klee's drawing, *Felsen Tempel*, transports viewers to imaginative places, characterized by mysterious temples and monuments. Similarly, the *Casa de Vidro* with its unique architecture and surrounding garden exudes a captivating atmosphere. The house appears to spring organically from the landscape, creating a relationship between the interior and the exterior.

The intent to emphasize the various relationships of the house to its surroundings is apparent even in Bo Bardi's initial designs, be it the immediate environment or the sprawling urban landscape of São Paulo in the distance.⁶¹ The house is situated at the highest point of a hill, offering a magnificent view of the metropolis of

São Paulo. The building was the first of its kind in the area, clearly visible to all, and was given the name “Casa de Vidro” by the neighbours.⁶² Originally, the Morumbi district was considered the “Atlantic Rainforest”⁶³ of São Paulo, a sparsely populated peripheral zone of the city until the early 1950s. Since then, the house has once again become enveloped by lush rainforest vegetation.⁶⁴

Today, the *Casa de Vidro*, or Glass House, is nestled in a small jungle. During the decades Lina Bo Bardi spent here with her husband Pietro Maria Bardi, she took meticulous care of the garden, planting all the trees herself.⁶⁵ Upon the completion house, it offered expansive views of the landscape comprising small farms and country estates on the outskirts of São Paulo. The glass facades of the *Casa de Vidro* provide a seamless visual connection between the interior of the building and the outside world. They not only let daylight into the indoor space and offer uninterrupted views of the outdoors but also create the impression that the boundaries between inside and outside are dissolving. In this way, space becomes more “fluid,” no longer clearly separated

by physical barriers. What is unique about *Casa de Vidro* is that Lina Bo Bardi planned it to be surrounded by trees. The trees were intended to serve as living design elements that would evolve over time and envelop the house, thereby making it a part of the natural landscape. This visionary approach speaks to Bardi’s deep connection to nature and her innovative architectural philosophy. Surrounded by trees and plants, the *Casa de Vidro* represents a harmonious fusion of architecture and nature. The *Casa de Vidro* was built during a key period of cultural modernity in Latin America, especially in Brazil. From the 1940s onwards, a distinct architecture developed there that was characterized by a critical engagement with European influences. This new approach to modernity found a particularly expressive form in the *Casa de Vidro*.⁶⁶ Klee’s drawing *Rock-Cut Temple* played an inspiring role in this context.

CASA DE VIDRO AND FELSEN TEMPLE: A HARMONIUS UNITY OF ART AND ARCHITECTURE

Bo Bardi’s *Casa de Vidro* can be directly linked to her 1944 essay “Case sui trampoli” (Houses on Stilts), published in the Italian architecture magazine *Domus*.⁶⁷ In this essay, she questioned traditional architecture and developed the idea of elevated architecture as a solution to practical problems such as flooding or wildlife. She aspired for a sense of weightlessness within architectural space and pointed to historical examples that embodied this approach. Thanks to technological advancements, particularly through the use of steel and concrete, this vision could be realized. Bo Bardi referred to examples such as the “pilotis”⁶⁸ of Villa Savoye by Le Corbusier or a simple fisherman’s house on stilts on Lake Maggiore (FIG. 14).⁶⁹ Her *Casa de Vidro* serves as a concrete example of this philosophy in which the house is raised off

Fig. 14

“The instinct sometimes builds parallel to the forms and tendencies of advanced art; this wooden house built by a fisherman on the shores of Lago Maggiore demonstrates, in the essentiality of its forms, the aesthetic features of the most modern architecture.”

Fishing hut on stilts at Lago Maggiore, circa 1944, photographer: Pinoli, published in: [Lina Bo Bardi], “Case sui Trampoli,” in: *Domus*, vol. 195, March 1944, p. 87
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archiv

the ground to respect and preserve the natural surroundings. The use of glass and the elevation of the house provide stunning views and create a dialogue between the interior and exterior spaces.

The Glass House is particularly distinguished by its static design concept and its striking main facade. The architecture of the building relies on slender concrete slabs and steel pillars with minimal diameter. Large panes of glass framed by subtle metal profiles make up the exterior skin. At the time of construction, traditional Brazilian building standards were still in effect allowing such a delicate construction. Under the new building regulations that were adapted to international guidelines in the 1950s, such a construction would no longer have been permitted. Nevertheless, the architectural design and materials ensured the required stability. With its lightness and transparency, the structure gives almost a “floating” impression.⁷⁰

Indeed, the concepts that underlie Paul Klee’s *Felsen Tempel* and Lina Bo Bardi’s *Casa de Vidro* present a fascinating interplay between two very different kinds of artistic expression: the two-dimensional and the three-dimensional. Despite these differences and the distinct cultural contexts in which the works were created, they both share a foundational interest in challenging traditional notions of space and boundary. In *Felsen Tempel*, Klee exercises his ability to render complex, multi-dimensional spaces on a two-dimensional plane. The drawing embodies an aesthetic of fluidity, which is central to the idea of “Liquid Modernity” – a term used to describe the way in which modern society is characterized by constant change and uncertainty.⁷¹ This is reflected in the drawing through the use of fluid shapes and forms, which suggest a sense of movement and instability. Through finely detailed compositions, Klee manages to blur the lines between interior

and exterior, matter and void, in a way that challenges viewer’s perception and encourages contemplation on the possibilities of space beyond material reality.

On the other hand, Lina Bo Bardi’s *Casa de Vidro* takes these notions and translates them into the three-dimensional space of architecture. The glass walls of the building allow for a fluid transition between interior and exterior spaces, emphasizing the interaction between the structure and the landscape that surrounds it. This is architecture that refuses to isolate itself from the natural world that envelops it. Instead, it promotes a dialogue between humans and their environment.

What is especially remarkable is how both artists manage to engage with the same core ideas despite working in vastly different mediums. Their works, in their own way, offer a vision of space that is not constrained by traditional boundaries or definitions, suggesting a more fluid, interconnected reality that reflects larger philosophical and cultural currents. In the concept of “Liquid Modernity,” we observe that Klee and Bardi approach the understanding of space in a manner that dissolves the dualities between interior and exterior, between human and nature, and between materiality and immateriality.

It is not necessarily a coincidence that Lina Bo Bardi chose this specific Klee work embodying these aesthetic principles from the Feigel Collection. She could have also considered the ink drawing *Idee wie ein Haus* 1925, 199, which not only explicitly features a house motif in both the title and the depiction but was also offered at the same price.⁷² Likewise, the oil painting *Mittelalterliche Stadt* 1924, 168,⁷³ of which architect Aldo van Eyck owned a variation under the designation *Mittelalterliche Stadt*, 1924, 167,⁷⁴ would have been another option. Yet, her choice fell on the work *Felsen Tempel*.

Fig. 15
Detail in the upper right corner of Paul Klee's *Felsen Tempel* [Rock-Cut Temple], 1925, 251 featuring the date and signature by the artist. [For full caption, see FIG. 8]
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Fig. 16
Detail from Paul Klee's *Felsen Tempel* [Rock-Cut Temple], 1925, 251: Infrared reflectography reveals underdrawing in the lower right quadrant, but not its motif. The addition is also visible to the naked eye. [For full caption, see FIG. 8]
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Fig. 17
Detail from Paul Klee's *Felsen Tempel* [Rock-Cut Temple], 1925, 251, showing the date and the work number marked down by the artist. [For full caption, see FIG. 8]
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Fig. 18
Detail from Paul Klee's *Felsen Tempel* [Rock-Cut Temple], 1925, 251, with the title of the work. [For full caption, see FIG. 8]
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It could have been Klee's composition in *Felsen Tempel*, in which he uses parallel lines as a graphical instrument to create forms and spaces, that inspired Bo Bardi to choose this particular work. It is undeniable that both Lina Bo Bardi's *Casa de Vidro* and Paul Klee's *Felsen Tempel* challenge our spatial perception in a unique way and encourage us to question the various ways in which space can be perceived and designed.

MISSING ENTRY FOR FELSEN TEMPEL

The handwritten work catalogue of Klee, covering the period from 1918 to 1926, interestingly lists another piece of art with the identical number "1925, 251" – *Waldarchitektur* – while *Felsen Tempel*, 1925, 251 is not listed at all.⁷⁵ This represents a rare example of double numbering in Klee's oeuvre.

The exact dating of *Felsen Tempel*, 1925, 251 (Z 1) was done by Klee himself and is noted in pencil in the upper right corner of the mountboard (FIGS. 15, 16).⁷⁶ Furthermore, another entry appears on the mountboard in the lower left corner: <<1925 "Z. 1.">> (FIG. 17); and in the lower right corner, the title of the work <<Felsen Tempel>> (FIG. 18).⁷⁷ This double numbering and the absence of *Felsen Tempel* in Klee's handwritten oeuvre catalogue call for further research and interpretation.

INTERSECTIONS OF MODERNITY: ROBERTO SAMBONET'S POSTER DESIGN, THE INSTITUTO DE ARTE CONTEMPORÂNEA, AND THE INSPIRATIONAL SOURCE PAUL KLEE

Another interesting parallel can be drawn to a poster design created by the Italian designer, architect, and painter Roberto Sambonet during the same time period as Lina Bo Bardi's *Casa de Vidro*, in 1951. When Sambonet began his career as a drawing instructor at the Instituto de Arte Contemporânea (IAC) in São Paulo, this

Fig. 19
MASP's first poster by
Roberto Sambonet, "Visit
the São Paulo Museum of
Art," 1951
© Courtesy of Archivio
Roberto Sambonet, Milan,
CASVA, gli archivi del
progetto a Milano

institution was part of a global educational network strongly influenced by European Modernism. This institute was Brazil's first design school and its curriculum was heavily inspired by the Bauhaus (1919–1933) and similar schools founded subsequently outside of Germany, such as Black Mountain College (1933) and the New Bauhaus in Chicago (1937).

In light of the industrial boom in São Paulo and the interest in participating in the international avant-garde, the principles of the Bauhaus, with their transcultural and cosmopolitan approach, offered a particularly radical orientation in the fields of art, architecture, design, and education. At the same time, they represented a counterpoint to backward-looking conservatism. In this environment, a kind of hybrid artistic language developed, influenced both by European immigrants as lecturers – such as Lina Bo

Bardi (architecture), Jacob Ruchti (composition), Pietro Maria Bardi (art history), and the previously mentioned Roberto Sambonet (freehand drawing and painting) – as well as by the native Brazilian students.⁷⁸

In this atmosphere, P. M. Bardi commissioned Sambonet to design a museum poster for MASP. The result was a labyrinth of lines that depicted a tropical forest with palm and sambamba trees – an imagery that added a fresh and tropical⁷⁹ note to a modernist template (FIG. 19). This portrayal suggested an engagement with Klee's drawing that is part of Bo Bardi's collection.⁸⁰

UNCHARTED PATHS: PAUL KLEE AT THE 1953 SÃO PAULO BIENNIAL AND THE JOURNEY OF FELSEN TEMPEL

Surprisingly, none of the artworks brought by Suzanne Feigel were acquired for the collection of MASP, whose new building was under construction at the time. Klee's work was first introduced to Brazil at the II São Paulo Biennial in 1953, where he was the subject of a special exhibition co-curated by Ludwig Grote. This exhibition was a major turning point in Klee's reception in Brazil, and it helped to establish his reputation as one of the most important artists of the 20th century.⁸¹

In 1972, to celebrate the museum's 25th anniversary, the drawing *Felsen Tempel* was printed on the flyer for the exhibition (FIG. 20).⁸² At that time, newspapers reported that this was the only work by Klee in Brazil. However, subsequent evidence has shown that additional works by Klee are now held in public collections in Brazil. The Klee drawing *Felsen Tempel* remained in the possession of the architect Lina Bo Bardi until her death in 1992. It was afterwards sold to the Mazzotta Collection in Milan. In 2008, the artwork was sold through Sotheby's auction house to the art collector Dorothy

Fig.20
 Invitation card for the opening of the Paul Klee Exhibition at the Museu de Arte de São Paulo on 22 August, 1972, with an illustration of Paul Klee's *Rock Temple* from the private collection of Lina Bo Bardi
 © MASP

Braude Edinburg and was later donated to the Harry B. and Bessie K. Braude Memorial Collection of The Art Institute of Chicago.⁸³

I would like to extend my gratitude to Osamu Okuda and Henna Keski-Mäenpää from the Zentrum Paul Klee in Bern, Diogo Horvath from the Instituto Bardi / Casa de Vidro in São Paulo, Bruno Cezar Mesquita Esteves from the Museu de Arte de São Paulo (MASP), Fabienne Eggelhöfer (Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern) and Wolfgang Kersten (University of Zurich) for their invaluable expertise and support, which helped to improve the quality of this work.

Special appreciation is owed to Roberta Saraiva for her essay, which provided valuable insights for this paper.

¹ Saraiva 2019, p. 284; Feigel 1993, p. 38.

² Paul Feigel, List of works contained in the crate G.A.M. no. 1, intended for the exhibition at the Museu de Arte São Paulo, 26.04.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo, 7 box 2, part 11.

³ Saraiva 2019, p. 284, note 1.

⁴ On 10 March, 1950, Pietro Maria Bardi, the director of the São Paulo Art Museum (MASP), reached out to U.S. educational institutions for curricula to help establish Brazil's pioneering design course at the Institute for Contemporary Art (IAC). Invoking the "spirit of the Bauhaus," Bardi outlined the institute's objectives (Leon 2018). His fascination with Paul Klee can be viewed in the context of the Bauhaus's influence in Brazil, as evidenced by the IAC's founding in 1951 and its activities (Leon 2018; Leon 2014). It's unclear whether Bardi's interest in Klee was kindled by Italo Faldi, an Italian art historian. Both may have been influenced by the 1948 Paul Klee exhibition at the Venice Biennale, featuring exhibition architecture by Carlo Scarpa. Faldi wrote extensively on Klee around this period and even hinted at a never-realized Klee exhibition at MASP (Faldi 1949; Faldi 1951). P. M. Bardi, a contributor to *Domus* magazine, was likely aware of Gio Ponti's critical review of the Klee exhibition (Ponti 1948). A rebuttal from Rodolfo

Pallucchini, the Venice Biennale's secretary, followed in the same magazine (Ponti/Pallucchini 1948). The 1948 Paul Klee exhibition continues to be a significant reference point in exhibition design and architecture (Okuda 2004; Ontano 2022; Mimmi 2022).

⁵ In January 1949, the Galeria Askanazy exhibited a selection of artworks that included originals by Kandinsky and reproductions by Klee. The exhibition featured 14 original works by Kandinsky and 10 high-quality colour reproductions of paintings by Paul Klee. See Saraiva 2019, p. 287, note 17; Bento 1949. The works likely came from the collection "Paul Klee. Ten Color Lithographs after Paintings," selected and introduced by Georg Schmidt and designed by Max Bill. The included works by Paul Klee are: *Composition, Tropical Twilight, Landscape with Yellow Birds, Flowers in Glasses, Ancient Sound, Little Blue Devil, Blooming, Full Moon in the Garden, Blue Night, Sign in Yellow*. See Klee 1946.

⁶ Saraiva 2019, p. 284, note 2.

⁷ Letter from P. M. Bardi in São Paulo to Suzanne Feigel (Frau Alimonda Haller) in Rio de Janeiro, 15.06.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo.

⁸ Feigel 1993, p. 38.

⁹ Ibid.; Letter from P. M. Bardi in São Paulo to Suzanne Feigel (Frau Alimonda Haller) in Rio de Janeiro, 15.06.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo; Arruda Botelho 2007. Lydia Alimonda Haller, born on 5 June, 1917, in Araraquara, Brazil, gained recognition as a pianist in South America and Europe (Feigel 1993, p. 38). She married Arnold Haller, a Swiss colour chemist whom she met in São Paulo (Letter from P. M. Bardi in São Paulo to Suzanne Feigel [Frau Alimonda Haller] in Rio de Janeiro, 15.06.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo). They relocated to Arnold's hometown Basel, Switzerland, after the war in 1945. In Basel, Haller established important musical connections, particularly with Paul Sacher, the co-owner of the pharmaceutical company Hoffmann-La Roche and the conductor of the Basel Chamber Orchestra, and with his wife Maja Sacher-Stehlin (Arruda Botelho 2007). Their friendship was so close that they

addressed each other using the informal "Du." Haller actively performed in cities like Zurich, Lausanne, and Geneva. A highlight was a concert in Zurich where she performed under the direction of Hermann Scherchen, playing John Powell's piece "Rhapsodie nègre" [The N-word cannot be separated from its racist origins. In scholarly discourse about John Powell, the term ("N-word") is retained in the musical composition "Rhapsodie nègre" within historically and philologically secured contexts]. In 1950, the family moved temporarily back to Brazil, first living in São Paulo and then in a house owned by the Votorantim textile factory where Arnold worked. Later, they moved to Rio de Janeiro (Avenida Rui Barbosa, Morro da Viúva). During their stay in Brazil in 1951, their friend Suzanne Feigel lived with them. Feigel stopped in Rio de Janeiro for the customs and to secure the release of artworks, including those by Paul Klee, for an exhibition in São Paulo. It's worth noting that Maja Sacher-Stehlin owned some of Paul Klee's works and personally knew him, as did the conductor Hermann Scherchen (Fuchs 2022; Okuda 2015, pp. 12–15).

¹⁰ Feigel 1993, p. 38; Saraiva 2019, p. 284, note 3.

¹¹ Feigel 1993, p. 38–39, 40; Silva Paiva 2011, p. 50.

¹² Feigel 1993, p. 39. The precise involvement of Jacob Ruchti in the exhibition project is currently indeterminable. Neither in Feigel's memoirs nor in the essay by Roberta Saravia, there is any mention of Ruchti. Jacob Ruchti, who completed his architecture degree at McKenzie University in 1940, played a pivotal role in the establishment of interior architecture in Brazil. He was a co-founder of the Brazilian Institute of Architects (IAB), the Museum of Modern Art in São Paulo (MAM), and the Institute for Contemporary Art (IAC) – the first Brazilian design school – along with Lina Bo Bardi and Pietro Maria Bardi. Ruchti also participated in the first Brazilian Biennials for Interior Architecture, both as a member in the assemblies and on the international jury. Furthermore, he taught Decorative Design at FAU/USP (1954–1961) and introduced Bauhaus principles, which he combined with modern Brazilian design. His projects, which questioned

modernist principles, were strongly influenced by the organic fluidity of Frank Lloyd Wright as well as the industrial modernity of Richard Neutra and Marcel Breuer. In addition, he was a member of the Brazilian Institute for Design and Construction.

¹³ Letter from P. M. Bardi in São Paulo to Suzanne Feigel (Frau Alimonda Haller) in Rio de Janeiro, 15.06.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo.

¹⁴ Letter from P. M. Bardi (secretary) in São Paulo to Suzanne Feigel (Frau Alimonda Haller) in Rio de Janeiro, 25.07.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo.

¹⁵ Lina Bo Bardi began designing a building for MASP on Avenida Paulista in 1957. The construction of the new museum began in 1960, but the project faced multiple financial and technical challenges that led to several work stoppages. The building was eventually inaugurated on November 8, 1968, after a construction period of roughly ten years. Queen Elizabeth II and Prince Philip of England delivered the opening address. Lina Bo was tasked with coordinating the opening exhibition titled "A mão do povo brasileiro" (The Hand of the Brazilian People), dedicated to Brazilian folk culture. In the new building, the Bardis continued their approach of an open exhibition space, using tempered glass panels mounted on concrete blocks to display paintings. See Getty/MASP 2018, p. 12 and Lanzarini 2020, p. 77.

¹⁶ Lanzarini 2020, p. 77.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Ibid.; Belchior 2015.

¹⁹ Frey 2000, see esp. p. 211 (on the travelling exhibition of 1947), p. 217, note 103, note 108 (on Feigel); and Frey 2005. After the passing of Lily Klee-Stumpf (1876–1946), Hans Meyer-Benteli and Hermann Rupf acquired the entire artistic estate of Paul Klee. Subsequently, they founded the Klee Society, which in turn established the Paul Klee Foundation. The assets of this foundation comprise approximately 3,000 works of art. In addition to his foundation and publishing activities, Hans Meyer-Benteli made an appearance with an article about Klee in the

Italian art magazine *Domus*. Cf. Meyer-Benteli 1947.

²⁰ The Museum of Modern Art 1949.

²¹ The extensive coverage of the comprehensive Klee exhibition in the USA ranges from major American newspapers like the *New York Times* (Devree 1950) and *Newsweek* (Anonym 1950) to Swiss media outlets, including the *Neue Zürcher Zeitung* (Sahl 1950), the *Luzerner Neueste Nachrichten* (Zaunkönig 1950), and the *Basler National Zeitung* (ag 1949), which reported proudly on the Klee exhibition in the United States.

²² Stefan Frey only mentions the travelling exhibition in the catalogue *Die Sammlung Bürgi*. See Frey 2000, p. 211 (on the travelling exhibition), p. 217, notes 103, 108 (on Feigel).

²³ Paul Klee-Stiftung 1948.

²⁴ Ibid., p. 11 [untitled foreword by Wilhelm Wartmann, pp. 3–11].

²⁵ The reviewer of the *Neue Zürcher Nachrichten* criticized Bill's positive assessment of Klee's art as "magic of pre-civilizational force" (Gr. 1948). E. Br. from the *Berner Bund*, on the other hand, praised Max Bill's "very conciliatory lecture on Klee," stating: "Max Bill, who is well acquainted with Klee's oeuvre and once personally received valuable insights from the artist who passed away eight years ago, gave a very conciliatory talk about Klee's life journey and the significance of his art in our time. He refrained from an in-depth analysis of his work, given the extensive existing literature. However, he succeeded in outlining the character and evolution of this art. Max Bill also guided the chronological arrangement of the exhibition, which is distributed in new rooms, and contributed to the production of the illustrated catalogue" (E. Br. 1948). The information about Max Bill's exhibition and his role in introducing Concrete Art to Brazil could be quite relevant in this context. There is a connection between the way Max Bill presented the works of Paul Klee and his own significance as a pioneer of Concrete Art. The mixed reactions to his opening speech in Zurich could be seen as an interesting contrast to, or even a harbinger of, his later role in the art scene in Brazil. Further

research is needed to understand more about Max Bill's critical remarks regarding Paul Klee's work during his opening speech at the Kunsthaus Zürich.

- ²⁶ Letter from Museu de Arte (Pietro Maria Bardi) to Rolf Bürgi, 05.09.1949, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bürgi Family Donation.
- ²⁷ Meeting protocol of the Klee Society, no. 50, 21 March, 1950, Zentrum Paul Klee, Archive.
- ²⁸ Silva Paiva 2011, p. 47.
- ²⁹ Ibid.
- ³⁰ Ibid.; Meeting protocol of the Klee Society, no. 50, 21 March, 1950, Zentrum Paul Klee, Archive.
- ³¹ Faldi 1951. Italo Faldi, born in Rome in 1917, was a prominent figure in the Italian art world. As author of numerous books, the director of various national art galleries, and a professor of art history at multiple universities, Faldi had an impressive career. He led significant galleries such as the Galleria Nazionale di Arte Antica in the Palazzo Barberini, the gallery in the Palazzo Corsini, and the gallery in the Palazzo Doria Pamphilj in Rome. In these roles, he substantially influenced the shaping and presentation of Italian art history. Moreover, he held key positions in the Ministries of Public Education and Cultural Heritage and served as the Chief Superintendent for artistic and historical assets in the Marche region as well as the Chief Superintendent for modern and contemporary art in Rome. Faldi's contribution to the encyclopedia article about Paul Klee in the *Enciclopedia italiana di scienze, lettere ed arti* (Faldi 1949) and the sources he cited demonstrate his intensive engagement with the art of Paul Klee.
- ³² Letter from P. M. Bardi (secretary) in São Paulo to Suzanne Feigel (Frau Alimonda Haller) in Rio de Janeiro, 25.07.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo.
- ³³ Klee held his only public lecture on 26 January, 1924, during an exhibition of his artworks at the Kunstverein Jena. The corresponding manuscript is held in the archive of the Zentrum Paul Klee. In 1946, the text was first published under the title *Über die moderne Kunst* by Benteli-Verlag in Bern (Klee 1945). Wolfgang Kersten transcribed this text in 1999 and supplemented it with a commentary about its genesis and publication. Cf. Kersten 1999a; Kersten 1999b.
- ³⁴ Letter from the secretary of Prof. P. M. Bardi to Dr. Meyer (Benteli-Verlag, Bern), 01.03.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo.
- ³⁵ Letter from the secretary of P. M. Bardi to Suzanne-Marie Feigel 25.07.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo.
- ³⁶ Cf. Neubauer 2022; Saraiva, pp. 287–291.
- ³⁷ Paul Feigel, List of works contained in the crate G.A.M. no. 1, intended for the exhibition at the Museu de Arte São Paulo, 26.04.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo, 7 box 2, part 11. As usual, the works were so-called consignment items, offered for sale by the owners through the gallery. For information on the ownership of individual works by Paul Klee, see the Klee Oeuvre Catalogue (Klee 2000, p. 394).
- ³⁸ Feigel 1993, p. 40.
- ³⁹ Ibid.
- ⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 41.
- ⁴¹ Ibid.
- ⁴² Saraiva referred to four works by Paul Klee that remained in Brazil and were sold, without naming them specifically, except for the piece *Felsen Tempel*, 1925, 251 (Z 1). Cf. Saraiva 2019, p. 285.
- ⁴³ Bardi 1954.
- ⁴⁴ On the journal *Habitat: revista das artes no Brasil* and Lina Bo Bardi, see Esparza Chong Cuy 2020.
- ⁴⁵ Tavel 2004, p. 124.
- ⁴⁶ Cf. MoMA; Okuda 2006, p. 100.
- ⁴⁷ Geelhaar 1973, pp. 98–106.
- ⁴⁸ Klee, BG. Cf. Okuda 2006, p. 100 and Okuda 2004, pp. 167–182.
- ⁴⁹ Klee 1923. Facsimile edition of the original manuscript and transcription in: Klee, *Schriften*, p. 126.
- ⁵⁰ Geelhaar 1973, pp. 98–106 and Eggelhöfer 2012, pp. 120–122. Klee guided his students to recognize the three types of lines – active, medial, and passive – in plant leaves. A subsequent handwritten note by Klee himself attests that he had conveyed this teaching material in an “abstracting” manner, and he refers to corresponding pages in his

“Contributions to the Theory of Pictorial Form.”

In these writings, the terms ‘active, medial, and passive’ are discussed in the context of the characteristics of lines. These concepts were first introduced in the lecture on 14 November, 1921, and revisited at the beginning of the summer semester in 1922. In his initial series of lectures at the Bauhaus, Paul Klee spoke directly about these three structure-giving properties in relation to visual elements. Only in the seventh lecture did Klee introduce a plant as a vivid example. This plant, growing from a seed through active force and culminating in a blossom, served as Klee’s illustration for the active, medial, and passive character of individual organs within the overall organism. Cf. Eggelhöfer 2012, p. 121.

- ⁵¹ Maria Stavrinaki demonstrates in her essay “Paul Klee’s Cave or the Prehistory of the Visible” (Stavrinaki 2016) that prehistoric themes first appear in Klee’s work titles during World War I. Examples include *Landschaft mit praehistorischen Tieren* [*Landscape with Prehistoric Animals*], 1917, 145 and *praehistorische Flora* [*Prehistoric Flora*], 1920, 146. On the topic of Klee and prehistoric painting, see also Seibert 2016.
- ⁵² Paul Klee developed his theoretical approaches to art primarily during his time at the Bauhaus and published them in writings and lectures. In his 1920 text “Creative Confession,” he emphasized that art does not reproduce the visible; rather, it makes visible. Other key themes included the study of nature, artistic thinking, and theory of form. His foundational teaching on design was published in 1925 in the Bauhaus books series under the title “Pedagogical Sketchbook.” Klee’s theories on colour and form, which were an integral part of the preliminary course, influenced many Bauhaus members between 1921 and 1931. See Eggelhöfer 2012.
- ⁵³ Okuda 2006, p. 100.
- ⁵⁴ In this context, Klee’s “Parallel Figurations” could represent a noteworthy connection to Semper’s concepts, as they translate basic geometric shapes – often found in architectural

constructions – into a visual-artistic framework. See Okuda 2006, p. 100.

- ⁵⁵ “Of these two arts [textiles and ceramics], textiles should undoubtedly take precedence because they can be seen, as it were, as the primeval art from which all other arts – *not excepting ceramics* – borrowed their types and symbols, whereas it itself seems quite independent in this respect. Textile types evolved within the art itself or were borrowed directly from nature.” Semper 1878, p. 12. Translation from: Semper 2004, p. 113.
- ⁵⁶ Okuda 2006, p. 100.
- ⁵⁷ Ibid. Cf. Bourneuf 2015, pp. 60ff.; Schäfer 2018. Klee taught weaving design only in Dessau from the winter semester of 1927 onward. In his lecture (Vorkurs/Gestaltungsunterricht) at the Bauhaus in Weimar on 19 November, 1923, Klee mentions the idea of weaving. See Buschhoff 2003, pp. 18–20.
- ⁵⁸ Anger 2004, p. 54.
- ⁵⁹ Geelhaar 1973, pp. 106ff; Okuda 2006, p. 100.
- ⁶⁰ On Lina Bo Bardi’s *Casa de Vidro*, which has become a key moment in the cultural modernity of Latin America, there is now a wealth of publications, e.g.: Oliveira 2012; Anelli 2019.
- ⁶¹ Oliveira 2012, pp. 22–24.
- ⁶² Ibid., p. 24.
- ⁶³ Ibid., pp. 22–24.
- ⁶⁴ In this regard, consider recent drone footage of the building and its surroundings, see *Casa de Vidro* 2023.
- ⁶⁵ Scarano 2023.
- ⁶⁶ Oliveira 2012, p. 22.
- ⁶⁷ The article is unsigned, but it was published during the years when Lina Bo Bardi and Carlo Pagani were in charge of the magazine. See Oliveira 2012, p. 26, note 3.
- ⁶⁸ Pilotis are freestanding pillars developed by Le Corbusier that lift a building off the ground. They serve as a load-bearing structure, create an open space under the building, and give the building a light and floating appearance. Examples of buildings with pilotis include the Villa Savoye, the Unité d’Habitation, and the Carpenter Center for the Visual Arts. Pilotis are a characteristic feature of modern architecture

and an example of Le Corbusier's innovative ideas.

⁶⁹ In reference to [Bo Bardi] 1944 and Boesiger/Stonorov 2015, pp. 128–129: In the first point of the architectural treatise "The 5 Points of Architecture," Le Corbusier and his cousin Pierre Jeanneret define "Les Pilotis" as a pivotal outcome of their intensive research, offering new perspectives for both architecture and urban planning. They describe a house built on stilts (pilotis) as a construction that is detached from the ground, allowing the garden to exist not only below the house but also above it, extending to the roof. The use of stilts (pilotis) elevates the house from the dark and often damp conditions found at ground level, presenting new possibilities for urban development. This concept was first introduced in German in the journal *Die Form: Zeitschrift für gestaltende Arbeit*, in the context of the 1927 Deutscher Werkbund exhibition and the newly-constructed Weissenhof Estate in Stuttgart (Le Corbusier/Jeanneret 1927). Since then, it has found widespread adoption in the architectural community. For more on Le Corbusier and Jeanneret's "5 Points of Architecture," see Oechslin 1987. Although Le Corbusier is commonly seen as the driving force behind the "5 Points of Architecture," it's important to note that architecture is often a collaborative field. Le Corbusier frequently collaborated with other architects, engineers, and thinkers. His cousin Pierre Jeanneret is an example of someone who worked closely with him. Nevertheless, the "5 Points of Architecture" were largely a product of Le Corbusier's own theoretical considerations and were promoted as his key principles for modern architecture. They were first articulated in the 1920s and implemented in some of his iconic structures, such as the Villa Savoye in France. It is true that ideas and concepts in the field of architecture are often shaped by discourse involving multiple contributors. However, when it comes to the "5 Points of Architecture," Le Corbusier is generally regarded as the primary author.

⁷⁰ Ricon Baldessarini 2001, p. 162.

⁷¹ "Liquid Modernity" is a concept by sociologist Zygmunt Bauman. He describes the state of modern society as fluid and being in constant flux. This "liquid" modernity brings both new freedoms and uncertainties with it, in contrast to earlier, more stable phases of modernity. In this "liquid" phase, both social structures and individual identities are constantly changing, and we can no longer rely on permanent structures for orientation. This has implications for various aspects of society, including politics, art, and architecture. Regarding the application of the term "Liquid Modernity" to Paul Klee, see Asendorf 2018: Asendorf emphasizes that Klee's work not only belongs to the history of painting, but is also specifically connected to developments in the natural sciences and humanities of the 20th century. Klee was not just influential to painters but also to artists from various other fields. This interaction begins at the Bauhaus, where Klee and other actors, for example, from the realms of Gestalt psychology or architecture, work on the question of the variable relationship between fluidity and stabilization – a central problem of modernity. Interestingly, protagonists from philosophy, music, and architecture continue to refer to Klee's work which appears in a uniquely open and adaptable manner, with ever-new questions even today.

⁷² Paul Feigel, List of works contained in the crate G.A.M. no. 1, intended for the exhibition at the Museu de Arte São Paulo, 26.04.1951, MASP Museu de Arte de São Paulo, 7 box 2, part 11.

⁷³ *Ibid.*, no. 9.

⁷⁴ Helfenstein/Rümelin 2000, no. 3539.

⁷⁵ Handwritten oeuvre catalogue by Paul Klee, 1918–1926, 1925, no. 240256 [pp. 236–237], Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern: <<1925 Z. 1.>>.

⁷⁶ The significant match when comparing the script of the numbers 2 and 5 between the date of the work title and the supplementary date <<30 12 25>> suggests that the date <<30 12 25>> was added by Klee himself. This is clearly confirmed by the infrared reflectography image graciously provided to me by the Art Institute of Chicago. The infrared reflectography also allows the underdrawing in the lower right

quadrant of the image to be displayed with higher contrast, although it does not enable the identification of a specific motif (FIG. 16b). The addition is also visible to the naked eye.

⁷⁷ Cf. Art Institute of Chicago.

⁷⁸ Ruchti 1951; Leon 2014, pp. 38-49.

⁷⁹ It's important to emphasize that the trees depicted in the drawing may not be perceived as "exotic" from the perspective of Brazilian viewers. This aspect is significant for maintaining the cultural perspective of the reader and to counteract any unintentional perpetuation of stereotypes about Brazilian culture.

⁸⁰ Rusconi 2020, p. 247, note 21. Between the years 1948 and 1953, Sambonet lived in Brazil. During this phase, he maintained a close relationship with Lina Bo Bardi and Pietro Maria Bardi, around the founding of MASP, which at that time was still located at its initial site on Rua Sete de Abril. At the then-existing Institute for Contemporary Art (IAC), he taught graphic design and textile printing. During this period, Sambonet divided his time between São Paulo and Massaguassú, a fishing village situated between Caraguatatuba and Ubatuba. There, he set up his studio and created landscape and everyday life paintings that later became the major works of his first solo exhibition in Brazil, organized by MASP. See Canas 2014, p. 11.

⁸¹ Saraiva 2019, pp. 287-291; Neubauer 2022.

⁸² Bardi 1972; Saraiva 2019, p. 287, note 14.

⁸³ Cf. Art Institute of Chicago.

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